

Deliverable 6.1

CHORIZO WEBSITE

D6.1

CHORIZO website

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Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Loss & Waste
BE	Belgium
CA	Consortium Agreement
CS	Case Study
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and communication
DE	Germany
DEC	Data Encryption Standard (websites, patent filings, videos, etc)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ES	Spain
EU FW	European Food Waste
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
GAss	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HUMAT	A socio-cognitive agent architecture in the SMARTEES H2020 project
IE	Ireland
IP1, 2, 3, ...	Impact Pathway 1
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L-H	Low likelihood – high severity
L-M	Low likelihood – medium severity
M	Month
M-L	Medium likelihood – low severity
M-M	Medium likelihood – medium severity

Acronym/Term	Description
MOA	Motivation, Opportunity, Ability
MS	Microsoft
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OEI	Other Ethics Issues
OTH	Other
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
PSC	Project Steering Committee
PT	Portugal
PU	Public
R	Report
R1, 2, 3, ...	Result 1
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations
SEN	Sensitive
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the deliverable D6.1 Project Website of the CHORIZO project. It has been prepared by FIAB and reviewed by CTIC CITA.

This report is a document which outlines the website to be used throughout the project in the dissemination and outreach of the products and services under development. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a description of the framework and backbone of the main public channel for dissemination of the project.

To have a consistent image and identity, a fixed visual identity comprising of the project logo and colours has been developed for the project website. The visual identity is applied to all the communication tools and channels that will be used in the CHORIZO project. This public website will contain project information, news events, conferences, newsletters, publications, press releases and social media. These tools have been selected in line with the communication objectives and target audiences of the project. CHORIZO website site will contain also a datahub, as repository of data collected during project works, which will be accessible by registration.

The CHORIZO website presents the main landing page for stakeholders interested in learning about the project. It is designed as a useful tool to be used by the partners and checked by external people from the project whenever they need information about how the project is organised and how works are going on.

1 INTRODUCTION

CHORIZO is a project funded by Horizon Europe programme that aims to improve the understanding between social norms, consumer behaviours and economic actor decisions and FLW generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, towards zero food waste. The project's main goal is to address existing research gaps and will use its outcomes to deliver and advance innovations helping actors to engage more effectively in food waste prevention and reduction activities. In short, it is a European project that integrates EC and food chain actors to enhance contingency knowledge and produce new effective instruments for facilitating successful transitions towards minimising FLW.

The project website is the main dissemination channel as a broad audience can be reached. Therefore, the website must be clear and will provide all necessary information to give visitors a complete overview of the project progress. In this sense, the website will be regularly updated with news related to technical results and topics, project meetings, conferences and workshops as well as news and articles of interest for the target audience. As an important factor, we will use social media channel to increase the awareness over the project and broaden the audience with news about CHORIZO project. In this deliverable, we present the first version of the project website, introduce the social media channels, which will be used throughout the project duration.

2 WEBSITE PRESENTATION

On the main page of the website, **Home page**, we have all the sections in the top horizontal bar and in this homepage we can find by scrolling down, general information about the project, detailed objectives, key project results and partners logos linked to each website.

In the top horizontal bar of CHORIZO home page we can find all the sections detailed below as well as project social media accounts.

- **The Project** with **General information, goals & results; The Methodology; The Work Packages;** and **Project Partners** (with all the logos, where you can click and go directly to their own website).
- **Case Studies** with general information on the 6 case studies to be worked on in the project, their descriptions, and objectives.
- **Media Centre** divided into **Dissemination Materials** and **Newsletters**, all available for download.
- **News & Events**
- **Contact** is available, where to receive any kind of request about the project or its work from interested parties.
- **DataHub**, repository of data results, to be discussed and created in a further stage.
- **CHORIZO social networks** included in website home page
 - Twitter
 - LinkedIn
 - YouTube

3 LINK TO THE WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

Link to **CHORIZO website**:

<https://chorizoproject.eu/>

Link to **CHORIZO social networks** channels

Twitter account @CHORIZOproject

<https://twitter.com/CHORIZOproject>

LinkedIn account CHORIZOproject

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/chorizoproject/about/?viewAsMember=true>

YouTube channel CHORIZO project HorizonEurope

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UckWWnjjslzWZyYCEg5wng4A>

Figure 1 CHORIZO website homepage

Figure 2 Case studies overview

Figure 3 Objectives diagram

CHORIZO PROJECT

